

A NEW DEVICE FOR THE MEASUREMENT OF DIMENSIONAL VARIATIONS OF ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS DURING CURE

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ABSTRACT

In several industry sectors such as aeronautics and automotive, composite materials have known a growing interest during the last decades. In order to succeed in optimization of the process, it is necessary to know accurately the material behaviour and its properties. In particular, thermoset composites undergo thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage during cure. These two properties have a high importance in the final shape and possible residual stresses of the part. However, since commonly used composite materials are composed of fibres and organic resin, their properties are often anisotropic. Several techniques based on volumetric dilatometers or through the thickness measurements allow determining dimensional variations of a sample during cure but are limited by their lack of multi-axial investigation. Also, thermoset resin matrix crosslinks, making the composite difficult to handle when a pressure needs to be applied. In order to overcome these limitations, a new home-made apparatus was developed; on which temperature cycle and hydrostatic pressure are applied on the composite sample while heat fluxes and transverse and in-plane deformations are recorded thanks to an original optical measurement. These deformations allow determining thermal expansion and cure shrinkage tensors during cure. Several tests were carried out in order to validate the measurements and first results from a thermosetting prepreg composite are presented. This work is a first stage that represents a new step forward in composite materials characterization during the resin crosslinking.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoset-based composite materials are increasingly used in several industries due to their interesting characteristics, *e.g.* high mechanical strength or stiffness over weight ratio compared to metallic alloys, flexibility, anisotropic behaviour... But their attractiveness may also lead to poor quality part if the material behaviour is not well understood and its manufacturing not well managed. Due to thermal and chemical volume changes during cure, residual stresses appear within composite parts. These stresses may lead to unexpected lower mechanical properties, shape distortions, matrix cracking, fibre buckling and other defaults. Numerous studies [1-4] emphasize the importance of such volume changes during cure on residual stresses development.

Despite numerous models of dimensional variations during processing were developed, only few measurements were carried out during the whole curing process. Several studies investigated volumetric variations of composite sample using plunger-type dilatometers, such as GNOMIX or PVT α devices [5,6]. Nawab *et al.* [6] studied an glass/epoxy vinylester composite and compared the chemical shrinkage coefficient (CS) for several fibre volume fractions under a 0.65 MPa pressure. The volume CS was found equal to 7.14% for the neat resin and 2.7% for the 49% volume fibre composite samples respectively. Even if these variations were accurately measured under manufacturing conditions, these methods only provide a global volume change but do not enable to differentiate dimensional variations along the different principal directions of the composite sample. A study involving the use of a laser scanning capillary-type dilatometer is reported in Holst *et al.* [7]. It suffers

from the previous defaults and is limited to isothermal and atmospheric pressure conditions. Daniel *et al* [8] determined the in-plane anisotropic components of cure shrinkage tensor using shadow Moiré method. Ifju *et al.* [9] also used a Moiré interferometry-based technique to determine thermal expansion and cure shrinkage of several stacking sequences of the same composite material during autoclave curing. Use of the laminate theory permitted to estimate the in-plane strains resulting from chemical and thermal shrinkage. Several other studies [10,11] were based on the same method to determine composite material chemical shrinkage during cure. Even though it provides strain evolution during the whole curing process, this method does not allow an easy and accurate estimation of the strain along different specific directions. The use of strain gauge to measure strain development during composite material cure is reported in [12]. But, as gauges react only when the material has developed sufficient mechanical properties, they do not allow capturing the entire history of the deformations. Multiple investigations of curing strains were thus performed using optical fibre sensors [13,14]. Among them, some authors use Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometer (EFPI) coupled to Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors [15] or FBG only [16]. These methods provide local information on the strain state but may be intrusive and are effective after the gel point only. Nevertheless, Minakuchi [16] was able to monitor the influence of the tool-part interaction on the in-plane strains for a T700S/2592 carbon/epoxy unidirectional composite under a 0.4 MPa pressure and temperature up to 90°C. For a specimen without tool, in-plane and through thickness shrinkage strains were the same and estimated to -1300 $\mu\epsilon$. Influence of the tool was clear and led to no in-plane shrinkage and a two times higher value for the through-thickness strain. Garstka *et al.* [17] were able to determine through-thickness sample dimensional variations using video extensometer. The effect of pre-consolidation was investigated as well as comparison with neat resin behaviour. AS4/8552 carbon/epoxy unidirectional prepreg was studied in the through-thickness direction. The average shrinkage was found to be 0.48% for a perfect UD and 0.98% for a cross-ply stacking sequence. They also determined through-thickness CTE for the cross-ply samples in liquid and rubbery states, leading to values of $3.73 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $2.02 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ K}^{-1}$ respectively. In [18], Olivier adapted a Thermo-Mechanical Analyzer (TMA) to measure in-plane deformations of composite materials with different stacking sequences. He applied his method to a unidirectional carbon/epoxy material and obtained CTE for fully cure sample in both transverse and longitudinal direction. Transverse CTE was estimated to $30.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $76.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ in glassy and rubbery state respectively. In their study [19], Jakobsen *et al.* also used a TMA to characterise thermal and chemical strains of a glass fibre mat/epoxy composite material in the in-plane direction. Their results lead to an in-plane CTE value of $25.9 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and a through-thickness CTE value of $46 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ below glass transition temperature. Following the same idea, Ersoy *et al.* [20] used Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA) to determine chemical shrinkage evolution of a composite material sample. Chemical shrinkage for an AS4/8552 carbon epoxy unidirectional prepreg was estimated to 0.64% in the through-thickness direction. However, partially cured samples were used in these last three studies, limiting the investigation of strains to post-gel state. Also, the use of DSC was necessary to have an idea of the sample degree of cure. Finally, Nawab [21] developed a tensile test on composite material samples draped on both sides of an aluminium foil. The sample was then bagged and placed in an oven equipped tensile testing machine. Results were obtained considering no tool-part interaction and no clamping influence. For a glass-vinylester unidirectional composite under a 1bar pressure and up to 163°C temperature, a 1.0% chemical shrinkage was obtained in the in-plane transverse direction.

The main objective of this study is to characterize the dimensional variations along through-thickness and in-plane directions of an anisotropic thermosetting composite material during the whole curing process and under manufacturing conditions, i.e. temperatures up to 200°C and pressures up to 10 bars. Thus a new set-up has been developed and allows capturing the sample dimensional behaviour with temperature, degree of cure and stress state. In the following sections, the new device and the experimental methodology are depicted. First experiments and results for a glass/epoxy composite are thus discussed and further developments are presented.

2 PRESENTATION OF THE NEW DEVICE

An overview of the experimental set-up is presented in Fig. 1. The sample is placed between a stainless steel plate and a stainless steel piston. The plate and the piston are set respectively on the fixed and moving frame of an Instron Electro Puls E10000 electrical press. Both plate and piston are located inside an aluminium cavity that can be filled up with BlueStar Rhodorsil 47 V20 silicone oil. Oil pressurisation is performed using an external piston, allowing a constant pressure from 0 to 10 bars with a ± 0.1 bar accuracy. An internal circuit allows the oil to thermally homogenise. Thanks to the electrical press, the piston applies a force on the top of the sample. Combined to the lateral oil pressure, the sample can be submitted to a biaxial homogeneous compression stress state, provided friction effects can be neglected. In this work, only identical lateral and axial stresses will be tested, thus leading to apply a hydrostatic pressure equal to the oil pressure. On top and bottom of the moulding cavity, two heat exchangers are fixed to control the cavity temperature. A Vulcanic Vulcatherm thermal regulation system ensures the cavity thermal control by circulating a fluid inside both exchangers. Temperature cycles can be applied ranging from 20 to 200°C, with a precision equal to ± 0.5 °C and controlled heating ramps up to 5°C/min. Each lateral side of the moulding cavity is equipped with a plane Schott N-BK7 10mm thick glass window. In front of one window, a KEYENCE LJ-V7080 contactless high precision in-line profilometer is placed to measure the sample topography along a line parallel to the through-thickness sample direction (see Fig. 2). The glass window and silicone oil being transparent according to the sensor wavelength, the profilometer directly captures the dimensional variations of the sample lateral side as a function of time. As the sensor is installed on a precise linear actuator, a displacement of the measurement line along the sample lateral side is ensured. Velocities up to 6 m/s can be reached using the actuator with accurate repeatable positions along its axis. Thus, the dimensions of the whole sample lateral side can be scanned within a short time and its evolution during cure can be recorded by this way. Simultaneously, the piston, monitored in constant force mode, follows the dimensional variations of the sample upper surface during the whole process. The different parts of the experimental set-up are managed using a specific LabView® program developed in the laboratory and the results are post-treated in Matlab®.

Figure 1: Global overview of the developed set up. 3D Conception (left) and 2D cut (right)

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Material and experimental conditions

A glass-epoxy quasi unidirectional (UD) prepreg (HexPly® Draft M34N/32%/430PUD/G-136x5) was used. It is composed of 90% of EC9-136 E-glass in the warp direction and 10% of EC9-68 E-glass in the weft direction. M34 epoxy system resin represents 32% of the total prepreg mass.

The composite sample was made of 16 plies of prepreg sheets by hand lay-up, all oriented in the $[0^\circ]$ direction. The sample was then cut using a die cutting tool and its in-plane dimensions were 105mm x 105mm. It was then compacted using a hydraulic press. A release film was placed on top and bottom of the sample to limit adhesion and ensure easy demoulding. The sample is thus placed in the mould so that the scanned side is the one in the weft direction (see Fig. 2, left).

Experiments were performed under prescribed pressure and temperature conditions. A 2.0 bars pressure was applied around the sample during the whole test. Temperature of oil and heat exchangers was held constant at 30°C for 3 minutes, and then raised up to 120°C at $3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The 120°C temperature was held for 40 minutes and the system was finally cooled down to 30°C at the same rate.

Figure 2: Lateral measurement principle and main directions (left) and optical adjustment (right).

3.2 Baseline subtraction and optical adjustment

During an experiment, the piston displacement is the result of the sample thickness variation in addition with the whole system thermal dilatations and compression. A baseline is thus performed under the same conditions but without sample. This baseline is then subtracted from the piston measurement done with the sample, leading to the sample thickness evolution only.

The lateral optical measurement also needs some corrections to be exploitable. The 405 nm wavelength KEYENCE sensor laser line is going through three different transparent media with different refractive indexes, *i.e.* the ambient air, the glass window and the silicone oil. The emitted ray goes through the different media orthogonally to the optical interfaces and illuminates the lateral sample surface. Lateral measurement is done by estimating lateral dimensions variations δ relative to the initial measured surface at $t = 0\text{s}$. Because the received rays are not orthogonal to the optical interfaces due to the KEYENCE sensor receiver position, the glass window and the silicone oil act as a plane parallel refractive plates leading to a shift in the measured dimensions δ' compared to the real one δ (Fig. 2, right). By using Snell-Descartes laws, one can obtain the relation between real distance δ and measured distance δ' . To correct the measured variations and obtain the real dimensional variations in the lateral direction, deformations have to be multiplied by the ratio of silicone oil refractive index over the air refractive index (Eq. 1).

$$\delta = \delta' \frac{n_{SO}}{n_{AA}} \quad (1)$$

Based on BlueStar specifications, silicone oil refractive index linearly drops from 1.403 to 1.400 for a temperature range between 20 and 120°C . For a real $100\mu\text{m}$ variation, this change of refractive index would lead to a $0.22\mu\text{m}$ measurement error, which is found to be negligible. Values of refractive index for the different materials are thus considered as constant with temperature changes and equal to 1.400 for the silicone oil, based on BlueStar specifications, and to 1.000 for the ambient air.

3.3 Device verification

Before using this new device, several setups were necessary in order to confirm the measurement feasibility and precision. These verifications are briefly detailed in the following. First, it was necessary to lower the possible friction opposed to the piston displacement through the upper exchanger. Alignment between the moving and fixed parts was checked using micrometric comparators. The only remaining force opposed to the piston displacement is due to the seal necessary to contain the silicone oil. Its value can reach a maximum value of 12.5 N, depending on the piston speed, which can be considered negligible compared to the applied forces. The lateral measurement was also checked on a gauge blocks assembly in order to verify the constructor specified sensor precision and repeatability. A 10.000 mm gauge block was measured through glass and oil. Measurements were corrected thanks to Eq. 1, leading to a 0.5 μ m measurement standard deviation and an error of 1.08%. To complete the previously exposed baseline and check for possible temperature-dependent phenomena, the whole system mechanical rigidity was checked for several temperatures from 20 to 180°C and applied forces from 100.0 to 2000 N. The system rigidity was checked not to change with temperature, its value equals 5.35 10⁷ N.m⁻¹ \pm 8.4 10⁵ N.m⁻¹. Once these numerous investigations were done, the measurement method was applied to a composite material during cure.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Raw data

First results obtained on the glass/epoxy Hexply prepreg composite are presented in the following paragraphs. Applying temperature and pressure cycle described in sub-section 3.1, the through-thickness and in-plane dimensional variations have been recorded using the press and the laser profilometer. Raw data from the press (Fig. 3) and the laser sensor (Fig. 4) are presented.

Figure 3: Through-thickness raw data from INSTRON Press and heat exchangers temperature.

From the through-thickness raw data in Fig. 3, one can determine three main time intervals which will be of great interest during results investigation. First, the 30°C isothermal step is not well assured due to the thermal regulation low efficiency at low temperature. One can observe a lag between the applied temperature and the through thickness displacement at $t = 750$ s. After what, the measured thickness grows linearly with temperature during the heating. In the beginning of the 120°C isothermal step, a temperature overshoot can be observed. This has only a small effect on the measured displacement and the isothermal step. The thickness remains constant for 500 seconds and then drops by a value of 0.05 mm, corresponding to the resin cure shrinkage. The thickness remains constant until the end of the isothermal step and then decreases linearly with temperature. From these observations, one can assume that the sample remains uncured during the whole heating step. The whole transformation occurs during the isothermal step and the sample is fully cured during the cooling step.

These assumptions are purely based on thickness variations observation and will be confirmed by heat flux sensors signal processing or DSC analysis of the resin.

Figure 4: In-plane raw data from the optical sensor.

Fig. 4 gives, for a fixed actuator position along the Y axis, the evolution of the sample lateral profile with time. The axis of lateral dimension variation corresponds to the Z-axis in Figure 2, whereas the position axis corresponds to the X-axis. The 28 mm and 32 mm positions thus correspond to the top and the bottom of the sample respectively. Some optical artifacts sometimes occur due to fibers spread during sample cutting. They are not taken into account during the results exploitation.

4.2 Results analysis and discussion

Several properties can be extracted from previous raw data. First, by analysing the lateral dimensional variations along the scanning line and based on the in-plane dimensions of the sample, one can obtain the lateral deformation over time (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Sample lateral deformation during cure for the 29.50mm position on the Y-axis.

The 29.50mm position was selected because it corresponds to the middle of the sample. Results from other positions are sensitively the same. From this evolution, it is possible to determine lateral thermal expansion coefficient for uncured and cured composite material as well as cure shrinkage. Considering the material as uncured during the whole heating step and totally cured during the cooling step and knowing the temperature evolution, the slopes of the deformation curve during these two phases directly provide the thermal expansion coefficients (CTE) in both states. During the isothermal step, one can notice a clear decrease of the lateral deformation, corresponding to the cure shrinkage (CS). The apparent cure shrinkage maximum value is directly extracted from this step.

The same analysis can be performed on the through-thickness displacement data. Thanks to the baseline, slopes during the heating and cooling are known for mould participation to the overall measurement. Raw data slopes are the sum of the mould related dilatation and the sample thickness evolution. By subtracting the baseline slopes, one obtains the sample related slopes. Once the baseline is subtracted, slopes during heating and cooling allow for the determination of through-thickness thermal expansion coefficients of both uncured and cured material. Once again, the decrease step during isothermal conditions gives through-thickness cure shrinkage. The different thermal expansion and linear chemical shrinkage coefficients are summarized in Table 1.

		Through-Thickness	In-Plane
Uncured CTE	[K ⁻¹]	3.17 10 ⁻⁴ (±0.02 10 ⁻⁴)	1.17 10 ⁻⁴ (±0.073 10 ⁻⁴)
Cured CTE	[K ⁻¹]	4.74 10 ⁻⁵ (±0.03 10 ⁻⁴)	9.04 10 ⁻⁵ (±0.058 10 ⁻⁴)
Chemical Shrinkage	[%]	0.77 (±0.008%)	0.12 (±0.006%)

Table 1: Thermal expansion and linear chemical shrinkage coefficients.

These results are found to be in good agreement with previous results. Through-thickness CS value is close to the ones found in [17,20], even though the studied materials are not exactly the same. CTEs of the uncured composite sample are higher than cured ones, due to the fact that as matrix evolves from a liquid to a solid state; covalent bonds are created between macromolecules, which lead to an amorphous rigid structure with a lower CTE. This evolution is commonly assumed and pictured in [17]. One can note a significant difference between in-plane and through-thickness values of the different coefficients (CTE and CS). For a perfect UD fabric, through-thickness and in-plane transversal values are expected to be equal, as can be found in [16]. However, the presented fabric is a quasi-UD, where weft fibres tend to hinder lateral expansions / contractions, justifying the differences observed between the coefficients. The same observations can be made on cross-ply composite samples and are reported in [17,20] concerning the CS and in [19] concerning the CTE distribution in a glass fibre mat/epoxy composite.

Several assumptions on the sample cure state have been made to get to these values. To accurately describe the sample behaviour, it will be necessary to identify the degree of cure with time. This will be done in a further study using heat flux sensors placed on the upper and lower sides of the sample. Heat flux signal study will give more information on the sample temperature and degree of cure, as is already done in another home-developed device [6] dedicated to the measurements of volumetric variations of neat resin and associated composite.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

A new multi-functional characterisation device, with controlled temperature and mechanical stress state of a composite sample has been developed to record its linear dimensional variations with time under manufacturing conditions (i.e. temperatures up to 200°C and pressures up to 10 bars). Compared to previous solutions, this device allows for the simultaneous recording of through-thickness and in-plane dimensional variations during the whole curing cycle. Thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage 2D components were determined from these measurements. The method was applied on an anisotropic quasi-UD composite material during cure. Results are coherent compared to previous studies and the obtained orders of magnitude are consistent with other studies of the literature. The current method is now being further developed to determine properties more accurately, whatever the

composite material. Nevertheless, these first results are very promising and allow a better understanding of anisotropic composite material behaviour during cure which is useful in the study of residual stresses development in such materials.

Several points will be studied in forthcoming works. Effect of curing conditions (i.e. pressure and temperature) on thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage distributions will be investigated. Efforts will be put on the understanding of the sample behaviour inside the moulding cavity, considering tool-part interactions. Also, heat flux sensor data will be analysed to obtain simultaneously the degree of cure evolution, which will be correlated with the chemical shrinkage. The Instron ElectroPuls press being able to apply a cyclic force with a frequency up to 100Hz, dynamic thermal mechanical analysis will be performed, giving more insights on the sample mechanical properties evolution with cure. Finally, the experimental protocol will be applied to a large variety of composite materials, with different fibre structures (UD, plain weave, stacking sequences...) and matrix (thermosetting or low-temperature thermoplastic polymers).

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